

RETAINING ELOQUENT ARTWORK'S OCCURRENCE: AN ANALYSIS

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Cite This Article as: Syahirman I, "Retaining Eloquent Artwork's Occurrence: An Analysis", International Journal of Social Sciences & Economic Environment, Vol. 3, Issue 2, Jul-Dec, 2018, pp 01-08, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.53882/IJSSEE.2018.0302001>

ABSTRACT

New forms of popular culture offered by globalisation often leave out traditional art. As a result, the nation's supportive community began to gradually abandon the native culture. The traditional theatre of mendu in West Kalimantan is one of the regional arts that "lives reluctantly dead do not want to." Artists and community leaders in West Kalimantan's Sungai Duri 1 area, Mempawah regency, founded the Tirai Budayaart gallery in response to these concerns. This gallery's mission is to protect and promote its distinctive culture. For example, it invites newcomers to take part in mendu's historic theatre revival. The study's goal is to shed light on the gallery's role in preserving West Kalimantan's traditional theatre, TiraiBudaya. It is a case study approach that employs a descriptive qualitative methodology. Afterward, a description of the function of the TiraiBudayaart gallery in preserving the traditional mendu theatre as a hereditary heritage and a West Kalimantan cultural treasure was produced as a result of the study's findings.

Keywords: West Kalimantan cultur, Mempawah regency, West Kalimantan's Sungai Duri

INTRODUCTION

No one can deny that modernization has had an adverse effect on society's traditional values. As a result, the supporting community easily uprooted and abandoned the tradition that was initially rooted. A nation's identity gradually transforms into new, foreign forms of culture.

Because it will be impossible to stem the stream of globalisation, contemporary culture will fill that gap as people's cultural values dwindle (2017, Jefrizal). Especially in the realm of art, this has a significant impact on the younger generation, which is more at ease with a fast-paced, practical culture. The younger generation's paradigm in enjoying entertainment appears to be shifting away from collectively enjoyed entertainment toward personal forms of entertainment. They are of the opinion that traditional art is out of touch with the current times.

The traditional theatre of West Kalimantan's mendu is one of the arts deemed out of date in the present day. The performing arts, in fact, are an important part of West Kalimantan's cultural mosaic (Effendi, 2006), but the community that supports them ignores this. Since modernization has had the effect described above, nearly all traditional arts have seen a decline, as if the living dead were unwillingly dying. Young people, in particular, are less interested in regional art than previous generations were (Kleden-Probonegoro, 2010).

Traditional performing arts played a significant role in society's culture a few decades ago, if you look back. Performative art serves as an educational, informational, communication, and social integration tool in addition to providing entertainment. People can also exhibit their aesthetically sentiments, along with their artistic expression and religious beliefs, through it. (Achmad, 2006). It's possible for traditional performances to serve as a repository for the noble values of a community's collective wisdom. The performance arts, which are also utilised to retain or seize power among people in a similar community, are part of oral traditions (Vansina, 2014).

Why does the supporting community find traditional theatre less appealing? This performance art is not only pointless, but it also appears monotonous. People in the millennial generation prefer to spend their leisure time on personal mobile phones or the internet. Entertainment has evolved from a group mode of communication to something much more personal. Lack of local government support also affects traditional theater's sustainability. The main key is the creativity and care of artists and, Lastly , community owners' involvement is crucial.

Concerning the issue of gathering young people to participate in traditional mendu theatre in his village's traditional art gallery, Various local officials in his village, including a singer named Syamsie Jar'ia, attempted to do just that. The TiraiBudayaart gallery is the name of the art gallery in which the exhibits were displayed.

Only the TiraiBudayaart gallery has been home to the mendu traditional theatre group in its current form until now. Since ancient times, there has been a condition that should worry anyone who knows anything about the mendu. To describe the gallery's role in preserving West Kalimantan's traditional theatre of mendu as a distinctive art form, this research is being conducted.

RESEARCH METHODS

This study employs a qualitative, descriptive research design. To describe something, you use a descriptive method. A descriptive method explains what you're looking at by describing it in detail (Creswell, 2015: 59). This study is qualitative in nature. There are a number of authors who have written on the topic: (2017) Using case studies as a research method, researchers look for as much information about the subject under study as possible in order to describe a case in depth. Case studies, according to Yin (2011: 1), are appropriate if the focus of the research is on current phenomena in real-world contexts.

Documents, actions, videos, and photos make up the data. Observational methods such as interviews and field work are used to gather information that will be documented and analysed after the fact. Mr. SyamsieJar'i, chair and head of the TiraiBudayaart gallery, was interviewed twice using audio recordings and records. An interview with actor and TiraiBudayaart gallery founder was conducted on August 25, 2017. In addition, during the mendu performance on the Sungai Duri 1 soccer field on August 21st, interviews were conducted with a variety of audiences, including the elderly as well as the young. At the

menduTiraiBudayaart gallery, researchers look at the training, preparation, and traditional theatre performances. Training and staging of the TiraiBudayaart gallery require data documentation as video-audio and photographic. Data from books, journals, and seminar proceedings are used to support documentary analysis. Data and information that the researcher deems important will be collected with the goal in mind.

Humans are the primary data collection instrument in this study, acting as both a tool and an instrument in his or her own right. To arrive at the results, the information was gathered and then analysed systematically. Using data reduction, data that does not match the formulation of the problem are streamlined, selected, classified, and then excluded from further analysis. In data presentation, data and information are collected, reduced, and then presented in the form of an organised description.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The traditional theatre mendu performed by the Malays of West Kalimantan is one example of their distinctive folk art culture. In 2014, the Education ministry Indonesia declared the native theatre of mendu in West Kalimantan and the Riau Islands as a "unique heritage treasure." Commend and respect the government's attempts to retain rich heritage, which is fundamentally a national cultural resource.

A Peek at Traditional Mendu Theater Province of Kalimantan

Dance, singing, martial arts, dialogue, and play all come together in Mendu, a traditional Malay form of theatre. An aristocratic saga is told in the play. The Beladon and Beremas dances open and close Mendu, respectively. While the dialogue and scenes in this play are amusing, the storey isn't. King Hadam (Adam) and MakMiskin (from the common people) play the cutest roles. One of the most important tenets of traditional theatre mendu is that good must triumph over evil in every play.

It is believed that the name DewaMendu is the origin of the name mendu. They came up with the name when they were preoccupied with rehearsals leading up to their first performance. Originally, the storey they planned to perform was called DewaMendu. As a result, the art of mendu was given an impromptu name.

Ramli (in Juliastuty, 2014) expressed a similar sentiment would often practise art in their spare time. However, they are unsure of the name of the art that they will perform when the time comes. It just so happened that DewaMendu was the subject of the first staged storey. They finally came to an agreement on calling the art form mendu.

The West Kalimantan mendu theatre originated in one of three ways: (1) in 1712; (2) in the 18th century; and (3) in the early 20th century. According to an ancient book written in Arabic and Malay letters, the art of mendu was first developed in 1712 Mr.MukmininNoerman (an old mendu figure) in Mempawah Regency's Malikian Village kept the book. 1871 was the year of the event.

The traditional Kalimantan theatre has its ups and downs. The traditional theatre of mendu was extremely popular in the community when it first began to grow. However, under Japanese colonialism, no performances of this play were ever staged due to a government ban

on public gatherings. The traditional theatre mendu made significant progress only after Indonesia gained its independence, in the 1980s and 1990s. It returned to decline even though it was almost extinct in the 2000s.

In the Heart of Eroded Regional Culture: The Tirai Budaya Art Gallery

The Tabir Budayaart gallery, which SyamsieJar'i established in 2007 in Sungai Duri 2 village and is no longer active, was previously run by SyamsieJar'i. Mr. Anwar served as chairman of the defunct art gallery. It ended up breaking up on its own due to disagreements among the gallery's members and especially because of opaque financial issues. Many actors have also relocated, which is another factor.

There was a meeting in 2015 to form an art gallery after SyamsieJar'i moved to the village of Sungai Duri 1. Despite the fact that the TiraiBudayaart gallery has no ties to the disbanded TabirBudaya art gallery, it engages in activities that are very similar to those of the TabirBudaya art gallery. The TiraiBudayaart gallery was established in response to concerns raised by young people in the Sungai KunyitSubdistrict who were losing sight of the unique art form of traditional theatermendu. It would be better if the younger generation gathered in a place where artistic activities could be done together rather than doing things that are of less use.

This event serves as a concrete example of efforts being made to preserve mendu's traditional theatre. It's not impossible that traditional theatre will go extinct if enough isn't done to prevent it. A gathering place composed of an art gallery, according to SyamsieJar'i, would make coaching and management easier. Since the art gallery must be formal and legally enforceable, the Tourism Office issues an operational permit. It has a Taxpayer Registration Number and a notarial deed to back it up (NPWP).

Furthermore, it's undeniable that this gallery was established to satisfy the desires of local residents, particularly parents, for art forms that were once popular in the area. In addition, some younger viewers claimed to want to know what their parents had told them about the distinctive arts. For the most part, the community watching mendu exists solely for the purpose of having fun and enjoying ourselves.

SyamsieJar'i is the director of TiraiBudayaart gallery. Additionally, he works in traditional mendu theatre as both a writer and a director (synopsis). Activities at the TiraiBudayaart gallery feature a variety of Malay arts, such as mendu theatre and jepin dance, as well as hadrah and kasidah, as well as folk songs. Regular training schedules are held to keep the gallery's activities going. Particularly for the weekly theatre mendu on Wednesdays and Fridays. The purpose of this workout is to burn off excess energy, not to improve performance. When it comes to training, the more intense the better if there is a schedule for staging.

During the anniversary, the 23 actors, 5 musicians, and 7 dancers all take part in the production. Three crew members assisted as sound, lighting, and equipment systems. There were approximately 26 members of the cast and crew involved in total. The following are the scripts from which they've performed.

Performing mendu is similar to other forms of traditional theatre in that no text is used. For the most part, screenwriters only write a synopsis of the story that will be presented on the screen. Others required players to be improvised and creative in both their dialogue and acting. As a result, players must be fluent in the local language without memorising the manuscript's text in order to play.

Mendu plays are known for telling tales about a fictional kingdom. For the TiraiBudayaart gallery's performance, the current context is combined with the play's subject matter, such as the dangers of drugs or forest fires, to pique audience interest. As a result, traditional theatre can continue to serve as a teaching and public education tool. This is where local wisdom's values can be reintroduced to the listeners.

Conventional theatre productions cost a lot of money if all of the props are used to their full potential. To save money, the TiraiBudaya art museum tries to stage a modest performance. In most art galleries, the back wall is covered with billboards or curtains that display the name of the art gallery. Tarp is commonly used to cover the stage's roof. All of the stage equipment is rented out. Even though a play usually has only one set, the stage can accommodate up to three. The ideal stage size for a performance does not have a standard size. Size of the stage is entirely up to the director's discretion, taking into account the field's size, the number of performers, the location of musical equipment, and the available budget.

Village heads in Sungai Duri 1 play a significant role in the fight to protect mendu. Mr. Suryani, the village chief, exhibited this when he took the initiative to establish the TiraiBudayaart gallery in the hamlet. His successor, who had a vested interest in the mendu's advancement, carried on this tradition. A total of five million rupiah is awarded for each performance. Unfortunately, the district government of Mempawah has provided no assistance. To help them, the District Government of Mempawah has invited them to events like the city's centennial or robo'-robo' celebrations. When invited to perform, the regency government always pays honorarium.

This appears to be a determining factor in the longevity of an art gallery. Many art galleries are stymied in their growth due to financial issues. There are no adequate rewards for the players. After a successful performance, it only receives inner satisfaction. In contrast, the labourers are average, the actors must pay a substantial portion of their own living expenses. Because their contributions take a lot of time and energy, they should have received compensation for them. That raises the question of how they'll be compensated for their efforts. A sanctuary (which, like the municipal authorities, lacks proper resources) or the local authority (which, like the sanctuary, fails to set aside a special coaching fund)? This is a critical issue for an art gallery's long-term viability.

There is only one instrument used to accompany the performance, which is a simple harp. Prior to mendu's rise to prominence, musicians played instruments such as the tawak-gong, drums, and violins, as well as the kesong-kesong (Chinese puppet violins). Violin,

drums, gongs, keyboards, and even sexepoons are used in the music performed at the TiraiBudayaart gallery. The musicians are an essential part of the show; they do not exist in a vacuum or as a subset of the musicians. That's why it's common practise to place musical instruments on the stage, usually in an obscure corner.

The actors are expected to be multi-talented when it comes to staging. They frequently take on two or more roles and perform numerous duties simultaneously. For instance, SyamsieJar'i had to work hard as both a director and screenwriter. In addition to performing the character of DatokPetala Guru, he also plays other roles. Like other roles, it's possible to play both warrior and music player simultaneously. They must also use cosmetology cosmetics during the show. Although, on occasion, the players will band together to make up for a mistake made by one of their teammates.

Mendu is always performed at night, which necessitates special lighting for each show. The researcher saw lighting done at a potluck without proper lighting techniques based on several observations made while gathering data. While there may be some light play during the performance, there is no dimming of lights in general or use of spotlights when the genie releases his magic or when there is a scary atmosphere. Sometime a twinkling series of lights is used to enhance the stage decor. 100-watt neon dangling lamps illuminate the four corners of the stage.

When entering the venue, the audience does not need to purchase a ticket. The TiraiBudayaart gallery uses this tactic to pique the interest of potential viewers in the mendu show. To make the performance feel more familiar and humorous to the audience, actors often include them in the performance by playing characters like Khadam or Mak Miskin. Also, As though the king were serving his subjects, the audience can be involved by giving gifts from the king to several persons. Traditional mendu theatre is known for involving the audience in the show.

Starting at around 20:00 West Indonesia Time, the show starts off with traditional Malay dance to kick things off. After everyone had gathered on stage, the scene kicked off with a Khadamfigure joke that had the audience in stitches. When it comes to the plot, the movie follows the synopsis and the director's instructions.

Researchers estimate that 400 to 500 people flocked to the area around the scaffolding during the event. Except that due to the short run time (about an hour), the audience began to disperse as one by one. There were only about 50 people left in the house when the show ended. The mendu that the audience was witnessing now differed greatly from the mendu that they had previously witnessed, according to some audience members who were interviewed. SyamsieJar'i is aware of this; she purposefully removed the old grip due to time constraints. It used to be possible to perform mendu continuously over a period of three nights, and sometimes even seven.

When it comes to young people, they are enticed to visit the location due to the large number of people already present. Despite the fact that some of them are already aware of the mendu staging due to public announcements and pamphlets that have been disseminated. Even though many of the young people who started watching mendu but didn't finish it were dissatisfied with the show's uninteresting storyline were curious about what it was like to be an artist. However, a 24-year-old man named Deo claimed he wished to join the TiraiBudayaart gallery in order to help preserve the culture.

There are times when the members of the art gallery gather to discuss the activities they have undertaken or simply to drink coffee in an attempt to survive in the fast-moving world of modern culture. The gallery has done its best to train both traditional theatre like mendu and kasidah and folk songs like hadrah (Malay). They're always concerned about unity for the sake of the gallery's long-term viability.

CONCLUSION

TiraiBudayaart gallery is the only traditional theatre group in mendu still in operation, according to the researcher who conducted the research. Some of the West Kalimantan province's menduart galleries have been vacuumed and are no longer active. To keep mendu's traditional theatre alive, a concerted effort is needed from a variety of sources.

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